

Carbon tax acceptance in a polarized society: Bridging the partisan divide over climate policy in the US

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Abstract. Political polarization in the US hinders bipartisan support for carbon taxes. Polarization operates unconsciously via implicit biases (implicit level), but it also arises when individuals consciously reflect on their political identity and beliefs (explicit level). We conducted two survey experiments with online panels of the US population to examine how irreconcilable Democrats' and Republicans' views on carbon taxes are. Study 1 compared measurements from an Implicit Association Test (implicit level) and stated beliefs (explicit level). Results show carbon tax fairness perceptions were already polarized at implicit level, but the main divergence in attitudes occurred at explicit level. Since explicit attitudes are considered easier to influence than implicit ones, Study 2 tested the extent to which message framing could influence this deliberated—explicit—polarization. We used different frames targeted at Democrats and Republicans to convey the idea that carbon tax support does not threaten partisans' political identity. Framings further polarized responses, increasing Democrats' but reducing Republicans' policy support. We discuss implications for climate policy communication in relation to navigating identity-based polarization.

Policy Highlights

- Political polarization over climate policy in the US is driven by the interplay of affective and cognitive factors.
- Unconscious fairness perceptions about carbon taxes are already polarized. These differences amplify when Democrats and Republicans consciously report their perceptions.
- Identity-affirming framings that appeal to partisans' concerns can influence carbon tax acceptance.
- Since Republicans may react negatively to climate policy communication, source credibility might be necessary to avoid backlash.

1. Introduction

Economists and policymakers view the carbon tax as a key instrument to mitigate climate change (Goulder & Parry, 2008), but voters are yet unconvinced (Anderson et al., 2019; Crowley, 2017). In theory, conveying the workings of the carbon tax and revenue use information should be enough to update voters' fairness perceptions, leading to an increase in policy acceptance (Carattini et al., 2018; Maestre-Andrés et al., 2019). However, accurate carbon tax information will only convince voters that strive for accuracy. These individuals are increasingly scarce as political polarization exacerbates, particularly in the US (Finkel et al., 2020), where political partisanship influences climate policy perceptions more than in other developed countries (Douenne & Fabre, 2020). Americans' political affiliation is the demographic characteristic with the strongest correlation with climate change belief and, by extension, with support for carbon pricing (Hornsey et al., 2016).

Democrats' and Republicans' divergent opinions about carbon pricing, such as different fairness perceptions (Sommer et al., 2022), can either be attributed to genuine libertarian beliefs (Smith & Mayer, 2019) or to motivated reasoning (Hart & Nisbet, 2012): Instead of striving for accuracy, individuals engaging in politically motivated reasoning aim to arrive at a predetermined conclusion that serves the goal of maintaining a prior standing belief, moral belief system, or feeling of identity within a group. The kind of motivated reasoning aimed at signaling and maintaining own political identity is known as identity-protective cognition (Kahan et al., 2007). As long as carbon taxes are perceived as a Democrat-leaning policy, identity-protective cognition might polarize responses.

Partisanship, as a form of social identity, does not only polarize conscious (politically motivated) responses but also fuels an unconscious animosity between parties (Iyengar et al., 2019). This automatic dislike and distrust towards any element related to the other party is known as partisan affective polarization (Iyengar et al., 2012). Biases generated by prior political beliefs and partisan affective polarization can polarize voters' unconscious fairness perceptions towards carbon taxes.

Although previous research has shown that carbon tax acceptance depends on policy fairness perceptions (Maestre-Andrés et al., 2019), no study to date has examined whether these perceptions arise at an implicit (i.e., fast, unconscious and emotional responses) or explicit level (i.e., slow, conscious and calculated responses). Yet, identifying the source of policy fairness perceptions is helpful to understand how irreconcilable Democrats' and Republicans' views on carbon taxes are. Disentangling the contribution of each mechanism to political polarization in the US has consequences for policy communication. While calculated attitudes like identity-protective cognition can be influenced by communication strategies like framing (Zhou, 2016), deeply rooted tendencies and emotions that arise at implicit level are less malleable (Druckman & McGrath, 2019).

We conducted two experimental studies to assess the level of deliberated polarization (i.e., the opinion divergence measured at explicit level) over fairness perceptions and strategies to bridge differences in policy acceptance. Study 1 explores whether the seemingly irreconcilable differences in carbon tax perceptions are deeply rooted in individuals' minds or mainly fabricated when partisans knowingly report their opinions. To discern the extent to which conscious responses exacerbate political polarization as a separate contribution from the differences already present at implicit level, we compared the carbon tax fairness perceptions measured with an implicit association test and a traditional survey. In Study 2, two different message framings were used to present the carbon tax as backed either by Democrats or Republicans, and the reported policy acceptance was compared. Our research contributes to motivated reasoning literature (Bayes & Druckman, 2021) by proposing this mechanism as a possible explanation to the deeper polarization observed at explicit level in voters assessing climate policy. We do not attempt to measure the prevalence of beliefs-based polarization, which will also be present at the implicit (e.g., priors about carbon taxes) and explicit level (e.g., libertarian political ideas). Instead, our reasons to hypothesize that explicit perceptions of climate policy are more polarized than implicit ones will be derived from identity-based political polarization. We discuss implications for carbon pricing communication relevant to policymakers and campaigners attempting to bridge identity-based political polarization.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1. Partisan affective polarization

From a social identity perspective, individuals instinctively divide up the world into an in-group and an out-group (Tajfel et al., 1979). Political affiliation, as any other form of group membership, causes both positive feelings for the in-group, and negative evaluations of the out-group (Billig & Tajfel, 1973; Iyengar et al., 2012; Tajfel et al., 1971). Although Democrats and Republicans have long regarded opposing partisans negatively and copartisans positively (Campbell et al., 1960), this tendency has heightened since the 1980s (Iyengar & Krupenkin, 2018). The intensification of partisan affect, fueled by political polarization, has exacerbated ingroup favoritism and out-group animus (Iyengar et al., 2019). Iyengar et al. (2012) coined the term ‘Partisan affective polarization’ to refer to the predominant dislike and distrust between Democrats and Republicans. Importantly, the concept of partisan affective polarization does not refer to ideological differences, but to a division rooted in affect and group identity (Iyengar et al., 2012).

Partisan affective polarization does not only trigger an emotional response towards individuals: Since all social information processing is affectively charged (Redlawsk, 2002), presenting a carbon tax to voters may also lead to an affect-based reaction towards the policy. The intensity of the emotional response toward the carbon tax will be determined by the extent to which this policy can be traced back to a particular political group. Before the motivated reasoner consciously processes the carbon tax, affect will be automatically activated to make an instantaneous assessment of the new information (Redlawsk, 2002). This heuristic mechanism that precedes more conscious thinking is known as ‘hot cognition’ (Lodge & Taber, 2000). Hot cognition occurs automatically upon mere exposure to a political stimulus (Morris et al., 2003) and biases individuals towards maintaining existing affect towards their party.

Given that US politics are characterized by partisan affective polarization (Iyengar & Westwood, 2015), any piece of climate legislation can be considered a polarizing cue. We hypothesize that hot cognition will instantaneously cause divergent affective responses among partisans, even before they have time to consciously assess the fairness of the carbon tax. If it

comes from the out-group, the policy will cause a negative first impression, regardless of its content (Finkel et al., 2020). We thus expect Democrats to have a more positive affective response because the carbon tax is mainly supported by members of their in-group (as pre-tested in Study 1).

H1: At implicit level, the perceived fairness of the carbon tax is higher for Democrats than for Republicans.

2.2. Identity protective cognition

Individuals' political identity not only drives affect-based reactions towards the out-group but also influences their judgment of policy measures. At explicit level, politically motivated reasoning increases polarization as partisans become more combative when defending their political identity and beliefs (Bayes & Druckman, 2021). While doing so, partisans try to minimize cognitive dissonance. As individuals strive to maintain coherence between choices and identity (Festinger, 1957), even supporting a policy can cause psychological discomfort (i.e. cognitive dissonance) if the position is not aligned with their political identity.

Cognitive dissonance can be avoided either by purposefully interpreting information to match one's worldview or by changing personal beliefs. A politically motivated interpretation of the facts is a less behaviorally costly option to avoid cognitive dissonance. Indeed, research has consistently shown that partisans react to climate change information by selectively crediting or dismissing evidence in order to arrive at a predetermined conclusion (Hart & Nisbet, 2012; Luo & Zhao, 2019). Motivated reasoning literature has used political identity to predict polarized responses such as divergent climate change risk perceptions (Kahan et al., 2012), the psychological reactance towards scientific consensus messages (Ma et al., 2019), and the lack of persuasiveness of climate change communication (Bayes et al., 2020). Identity-protective cognition, a type of motivated reasoning, facilitates individuals' interpretation of information in a way that agrees with the views held by their fellow partisans (Kahan, 2015; Kahan et al., 2017). Motivated reasoners involved in identity-protective cognition resort to mechanisms such as confirmation bias (i.e., the desire to be consistent with one's existing beliefs influences

information prioritization) (Druckman & McGrath, 2019). Confirmation bias reduces individuals' likelihood of being influenced by peers with different views (Konc & Savin, 2019). This could explain why the opinions expressed by individuals generally reflect the beliefs that predominate in their in-group (Kahan, 2017). As a result, voters will agree more easily with propositions consistent with the beliefs of their political tribe, while they will react against dissonant information threatening their political identity (Ma et al., 2019; Nisbet et al., 2015).

Since supporting the implementation of a new tax to mitigate climate change might be at odds with mainstream Republican behavior, exposure to carbon tax information could trigger identity-protective cognition among Republicans. Similarly, Douenne & Fabre (2022) attributed their results to motivated reasoning when they found that political opponents of the carbon tax tended to discard positive information about the policy and overestimate its negative impacts. Perceiving the carbon tax as a Democrat-leaning policy may polarize the responses of individuals (e.g., Republicans) whose identity-protective cognition nudges them towards maintaining their membership of their political tribe (e.g., not aligning with Democrats' policies). Besides, voters' contrary or favorable opinions on an openly partisan policy can be tainted by the willingness to express their political affiliation (Huddy et al., 2015).

Apart from the issue-based polarization driven by genuine libertarian beliefs, identity-protective cognition may further polarize the fairness perception of the carbon tax if individuals have time to consciously process the policy measure and are aware that their response is being recorded (e.g., when filling in a questionnaire). We hypothesize that Democrats will assess the carbon tax positively in a survey while Republicans will assess it negatively.

H2: At explicit level, the perceived fairness of the carbon tax is higher (and positive) for Democrats than for Republicans, who will evaluate the tax negatively.

2.3. Affective and cognitive factors widening the partisan gap

Partisan affective polarization and identity protective cognition may polarize carbon tax fairness perceptions at implicit and explicit levels, respectively. Recent systematic studies on the dynamics of climate policy support have revealed the complex and central role of political views on opinion

formation (Konc et al., 2022). Yet, climate change-related political polarization literature remains disproportionately focused on deliberated motivated reasoning while affect-driven heuristics have received insufficient attention (Bayes & Druckman, 2021; Hennes et al., 2020). From a dual-process theory perspective (Chaiken & Trope, 1999), deliberated motivated reasoning constitutes an incomplete explanation of political polarization because affective evaluations that are independent from cognitive processing can impact perceptions too (Way & Masters, 1996). For example, Rinscheid and Wüstenhagen (2018) showed that Swiss voters' decision to phase out nuclear power was heavily influenced by an affect heuristic, to the extent that the interplay of cognitive and affective factors led to an opinion swing.

In the same line, identity-based political polarization may be driven by the interplay of two distinct mechanisms: An unconscious group identity affect (i.e., partisan affective polarization) and a deliberated avoidance of cognitive dissonance by aligning personal perceptions with own political identity (i.e., identity-protective cognition). This would imply that affective and cognitive factors influenced by political identity make separate contributions to the partisan gap, namely, to the difference between Democrats' and Republicans' perceptions.

Since affect-based reactions occur faster than conscious cognitive processing (Weber & Johnson, 2009), the implicitly measured partisan gap will only capture the differences created by implicit biases. At explicit level, cognitive factors like identity-protective cognition add to the polarizing influence of these affective factors, exacerbating deliberated polarization. Therefore, we expect the partisan gap at explicit level to be wider because it will be influenced by both affective and cognitive factors.

H3: The partisan gap, calculated as the difference between Democrats' and Republicans' carbon tax fairness perception, will be wider at the explicit level than at the implicit level.

2.4. Circumventing identity protective cognition

Individuals resorting to identity-protective cognition to process climate change-related messages can evaluate new information as either threatening or non-threatening to their identity or beliefs (Druckman & McGrath, 2019). Non-threatening information is normally perceived as more

credible (Cohen & Sherman, 2014). Source credibility leads to persuasion when partisans think the message is endorsed by their political party (Linde, 2018). Rather than the message content, it is source credibility what influences individuals' opinions (Goren et al., 2009). Messages targeting specific political identities can thus be used to influence individuals' fairness perceptions and increase carbon tax acceptance. This is consistent with previous research showing that individuals' skepticism towards climate change communication can be reduced using identity-affirming framings that support a new opinion formation process without feeling at odds with their identity (Kahan et al., 2015; Wolsko et al., 2016).

When the use of tax revenue as a progressive revenue redistribution program is highlighted, voters might infer the carbon tax is a Democrats' policy, while a carbon tax message using personal freedom and free-market rhetoric might convey that the carbon tax is endorsed by Republicans. Since Republicans are more susceptible to climate policy framing interventions (Rode & Ditto, 2021), our hypotheses focus on Republicans' reactions. We assume climate policy support will already be part of Democrats' political convictions. Besides, Democrats' perceptions are more stable after interventions (Hardisty et al., 2010) partly because message framing effects are larger when climate change concern is low (Newman et al., 2012). We predict that message framing can influence carbon tax acceptance, either deepening or bridging deliberated polarization.

H4a: A message framing that highlights distributional fairness (seemingly a Democrat argumentation) reduces carbon tax acceptance among Republicans.

H4b: A message framing that highlights personal fairness (seemingly a Republican argumentation) increases carbon tax acceptance among Republicans.

3. Overview of the studies

We conducted two studies to test the proposed hypotheses. Study 1 compared partisans' implicit (H1) and explicit (H2) fairness perceptions about the carbon tax and checked whether differences between Democrats' and Republicans' perceptions were greater at explicit level (H3). Study 2 tested whether partisans' reported carbon tax acceptance can be influenced by framing strategies

highlighting distributional (H4a) and personal fairness (H4b). See Appendix A for further information on sample characteristics, study designs, data analysis and manipulation checks.

Following open science best practices, we disclose the materials, datasets and code to replicate our analyses. These files are available as an Open Science Framework (OSF) project at: https://osf.io/mjxv9/?view_only=27d2c3fc8b4c4b3fb1bc672cb630b5da

4. Study 1

4.1. Method

4.1.1. Participants and procedure

We recruited a random sample of 405 participants (202 Democrats and 203 Republicans) from a Prolific online panel of the US population (49.60% female, $M_{\text{age}} = 45.32$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 14.68$). Participants completed a survey built in Qualtrics software that consisted of a questionnaire preceded by an Implicit Association Test (IAT). To integrate the IAT in a survey that also contained explicit questions, we used the JavaScript-based IAT for Qualtrics developed by Carpenter et al. (2019). Their procedure maximizes IAT reliability because it follows Greenwald et al.'s (2003) and Lane et al.'s (2007) recommendations step-by-step.

The IAT assigned participants tasks designed to implicitly measure respondents' unconscious associations. The resulting implicit bias is a relative measure of the strength of the association between two contrasted concepts (e.g., flower vs. insect) and two contrasted attributes (e.g., pleasant vs. unpleasant). Therefore, the stimuli included in the IAT also featured the concept of regular consumption taxes and the attribute of unfairness, which allowed comparing concepts (carbon taxes vs. consumption taxes) and attributes (fair vs. unfair). The consumption taxes were presented as neutral as possible because their sole purpose was to serve as a benchmark to compare the relative fairness of the carbon tax with that of a non-partisan equivalent.

The survey began with the IAT. Firstly, participants read a brief text describing carbon taxes and consumption taxes to ensure they understood the concepts (See Appendix A for exact wording and a manipulation check confirming the carbon tax was viewed as a Democrat-leaning policy). Thereafter, participants placed their hands on the keyboard and completed seven blocks of stimuli

sorting trials. In each trial, a word appeared on the screen representing an attribute (e.g., equitable) or a concept (e.g., Environmental tax). Participants were instructed to sort the stimulus as fast as possible by pressing a given keyboard key with the designated hand (e.g., left for carbon tax or fair; right for consumption tax or unfair). Since concepts and attributes were presented reversed in different blocks, participants had to make an extra effort to override their existing mental associations, which slowed down their responses. One can more rapidly sort stimuli when pairings are compatible with internal beliefs (Greenwald et al., 1998). Therefore, the degree to which participants were faster in one block or the other was taken as a measure of their implicit bias (Lane et al., 2007). In this case, the sorting tasks were aimed at examining whether carbon taxes were easier associated with fairness than consumption taxes were.

Participants completed the procedure seven times (seven blocks), allowing for switching attributes and concepts. Three blocks consisted of 20 practice trials that served to familiarize participants with the stimuli and sorting procedure, while the remaining combined blocks were divided into a 20-trial practice part and a 40-trial critical part. The survey concluded with a questionnaire explicitly asking participants to report on their perceived fairness of a carbon tax and a neutral consumption tax. Appendix A provides more details about the survey (Figures A.1-A.3).

4.1.2. Measures

The concepts and attributes used in the IAT are represented by several stimuli that participants interact with. We decided to use 6 stimuli per category, as previous studies and methodological recommendations usually suggest a number between 4 and 6 (Greenwald et al., 1998; Pogacar et al., 2019). The stimuli related to the carbon tax were obtained from the most common terms used in literature review searches (e.g., Maestre-Andrés et al. (2019)): *Climate tax, ecological tax, energy tax, environmental tax, and pollution tax*. The selection of the stimuli representing neutral consumption taxes was based on their commonness and familiarity, prioritizing the ones participants might be already acquainted with, like the retail sales tax. A list of neutral consumption taxes, as well as words related to the *fairness* and *unfairness* attributes, were pre-

tested and further refined after a qualitative discussion session with five scholars experienced in IAT. Since moral and emotional language is more likely to reveal polarization (Van Bavel & Pereira, 2018), the selected attributes were not necessarily synonyms of *fairness* and *unfairness* but rather uplifting or negative related words. Table A.2 in Appendix A shows the list of stimuli used in the IAT.

A standardized difference score known as the D-score (Greenwald et al., 2003) was calculated for each participant based on how fast they sorted the words in each block. This implicit fairness measure was reliable (See Appendix A). Positive D-scores indicated carbon taxes were implicitly perceived as fairer than neutral consumption taxes, while negative D-scores meant that carbon taxes were perceived as less fair than consumption taxes.

Regarding explicit responses, the perceived fairness measure was adapted from the procedural fairness construct used by Colquitt and Rodell (2015). Participants reported the extent to which they agreed with five statements describing both a carbon tax and a neutral consumption tax (Value Added Tax) on a 5-point Likert scale from *strongly disagree* = 1 to *strongly agree* = 5. The exact wording of the scale items and construct information is provided in Appendix A. The reliability of the explicit fairness measures obtained for carbon taxes ($\alpha = .80$) and consumption taxes ($\alpha = .78$) was confirmed before analyzing the data. As with the D-scores from the IAT, the positive values of this explicit relative fairness measure indicated carbon taxes were perceived as fairer than neutral consumption taxes, while negative values meant that participants assessed the carbon tax as less fair than a neutral consumption tax.

4.2. Results

The implicit fairness (M_i) and explicit fairness (M_e) measures were positively correlated ($r = .31$, $P < .001$). At implicit level, the bias towards associating carbon taxes with unfairness was significantly stronger for Republicans ($M_{i,rep} = -0.45$, $SD_{i,rep} = 0.45$) than for Democrats ($M_{i,dem} = -0.21$, $SD_{i,dem} = 0.55$; $\Delta M_i = 0.24$, 95% CI (0.14, 0.34), $t(392) = 4.76$, $P < 0.001$, $d = 0.48$), confirming H1. The majority of the sample (77%) had negative (< 0 ; i.e., unfairness) associations (Figure 1a). Although most participants implicitly regarded carbon taxes as unfair relative to

neutral consumption taxes, Democrats still tended towards more positive unconscious associations (Figure 1b).

Figure 1. Density plots of implicit and explicit fairness perceptions.

The homogeneous fairness perceptions at implicit level contrast with the more dispersed fairness perceptions explicitly reported by participants. Almost half of the sample (48%) had a positive fairness perception of the carbon tax, relative to a neutral consumption tax (Figure 1c). The higher variability was caused by Democrats' and Republicans' fairness perceptions being more polarized at explicit level (Figure 1d). While Republicans consistently perceived carbon taxes as unfair ($M_{e,rep} = -0.72$, $SD_{e,rep} = 1.05$), Democrats rated the carbon tax as fairer than a neutral consumption tax ($M_{e,dem} = 0.20$, $SD_{e,dem} = 1.08$; $\Delta M_e = 0.91$, 95% CI (0.70, 1.12), $t(392) = 8.50$, $P < 0.001$, $d = 0.86$), corroborating H2. The partisan gap more than doubled at explicit level, relative to its size at implicit level: the significant difference in effect sizes ($Z = 2.54$, $P = 0.005$)

confirmed that explicit fairness responses were more polarized than the implicit fairness associations, providing support for H3.

4.3. Discussion

At implicit level, the significant differences between Democrats' and Republicans' fairness perceptions confirmed that the mere exposure to a carbon tax triggers a polarizing emotional reaction. Republicans implicitly evaluated carbon taxes more negatively than Democrats. This implicit partisan gap was measured with an IAT to ensure the association was unconscious. Automatic responses denote tendencies to favor elements that come from the in-group and dislike the out-group (Iyengar & Westwood, 2015). Since the measured implicit associations were instantaneous, the emotional responses were driven either by partisan affective polarization (Iyengar et al., 2012) or priors about the policy.

At explicit level, participants' carbon tax fairness perceptions were more polarized. Democrats rated the carbon tax as a fair policy measure, distancing themselves from Republicans, who consistently evaluated it negatively. As expected, the explicit partisan gap was wider than the implicit partisan gap. Polarization was exacerbated when participants had the opportunity to consciously assess the policy measure, doubling the size of the partisan gap. The wider partisan gap at explicit level is a product of the interplay of cognitive and affective factors: In addition to the implicit biases triggered by policy priors and partisan affect, conscious processing of the information may have also led participants to reflect on their libertarian beliefs and to some sort of motivated reasoning. The extent to which this deliberated motivated reasoning is issue-based or identity-based is beyond the scope of this study. But given that identity-based polarization is more divisive than issue-based polarization in US politics (Mason, 2015), identity protective cognition might have particularly contributed to the widening of the partisan gap at explicit level. Conscious assessments of carbon tax fairness are probably influenced by the same identity-based polarization that created the unconscious divisions, as suggested by the significant correlation between the implicit and the explicit measures of our study.

The possible presence of identity protective-cognition is consistent with a wide explicit partisan gap because motivated reasoners with identity-protective goals hardly deviate from the political ideas common to their in-group. Aside from protecting group membership, motivated reasoning can also pursue self-expressive benefits (Bullock et al., 2015) or lead to different expressive responding reactions like ‘partisan cheerleading’ (McGrath, 2017). Even though these mechanisms offer complementary explanations to identity-protective cognition, they are all based on the assumption that partisans’ responses will be influenced by their political identity.

5. Study 2

5.1 Method

5.1.1 Participants and procedure

We conducted an online experiment using Qualtrics survey software. A sample of 300 participants was drawn from a Prolific online panel of the US population (51.00% female, $M_{\text{age}} = 38.11$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 13.16$). Half of the participants ($n = 150$) identified themselves as Republicans, while the other half identified as Democrats. Participants were assigned to one of three experimental factor treatments (control vs. distributional fairness framing vs. personal fairness framing), maintaining the balance of political orientation in each experimental cell.

To ensure all participants understood what a carbon tax is, they first read a brief text describing the measure: “*A carbon tax is a levy that polluters pay on the carbon emissions they emit. This encourages people and businesses to make choices and investments that are good for the environment.*” This neutral presentation of carbon taxes was extracted from the World Bank’s Guide to Communicating Carbon Pricing (Partnership for Market Readiness 2018, p. 58). Only participants in the message framing experimental groups were provided with additional explanations about why carbon taxes were fair. After the neutral description of the carbon tax, the framed message presented to the distributional fairness group continued as follows: “*The carbon tax is a fair policy because it raises money that can be returned to taxpayers in the form of lump-sum payments to support low-income groups and disproportionately affected communities transitioning out of high-carbon industries*”. Conversely, the personal fairness group were told

that “*The carbon tax is a fair policy because it does not limit freedom of choice of businesses and individuals like you: Carbon taxes replace unnecessarily complicated government regulations with transparent, flexible and simple market-based incentives*”.

Narratives emphasizing group-specific value orientations should be attractive to political partisans (Aasen, 2017). The distributional fairness framing was aimed at appealing to Democrats’ concerns, while the objective of the personal fairness framing was to resonate with Republicans. The message design was informed by the list of carbon tax fairness concerns collected by Maestre-Andrés et al. (2019). We also crosschecked that the wording of the framing manipulations reflected the concerns voiced by citizens in an open-ended survey about carbon tax fairness (Savin et al., 2020). After exposure to the experimental stimuli, all participants responded to the same online questionnaire. See Appendix A for the manipulation checks on framing effectiveness.

5.1.2 Measures

Based on the carbon tax description they read, participants were asked to rate the acceptability of the carbon tax using a 5-point Likert scale (*not acceptable* = 1 to *very acceptable* = 5) on two measurement items: “*How acceptable do you find this carbon tax?*” and “*Do you think taxing carbon emissions is an acceptable policy measure?*”. These items have been consistently used in previous research (Dreyer et al., 2015; Maestre-Andrés et al., 2021; Unsworth & Fielding, 2014). The resulting carbon tax acceptance construct was internally consistent ($\alpha = 0.95$)

The same scale from Study 1 was used to measure participants’ perceived fairness with three items adapted from Colquitt and Rodell (2015), which again formed a reliable procedural fairness construct ($\alpha = 0.85$). The 5-point Likert scale also ranged from *strongly disagree* = 1 to *strongly agree* = 5. The questionnaire concluded with demographic questions, including political orientation questions on liberal, conservative, green and libertarian beliefs (using a 5-point Likert scale). The liberal and conservative political orientation questions were used to verify that the sample pre-screening was reliable. Participants’ libertarian beliefs and environmental values were measured as control variables (See Appendix A). Before finishing, in an open-ended question,

participants were asked what they thought was the objective of the survey. Since none of the participants guessed the purpose of the experiment, it is unlikely that responses are biased due to expectancy effects.

5.2 Results

A two-way ANOVA was conducted to examine the effects of message framing and political orientation on carbon tax acceptance. There was a statistically significant interaction between message framing and political orientation on carbon tax acceptance, $F(2, 294) = 3.40, P = 0.035, \eta_p^2 = 0.02$. We performed an analysis of simple main effects for political orientation with statistical significance receiving a Bonferroni adjustment and being accepted at the $P < 0.025$ level. Table 1 shows that Democrats reported a significantly higher carbon tax acceptance in all experimental groups. Compared to the control group, both framing manipulations widened the gap between Democrats' and Republicans' responses, which suggested an interaction effect.

Table 1. Mean carbon tax acceptance, by experimental group and political orientation.

Experimental group	N	Political orientation		Mean difference	F	P	η_p^2
		Democrat	Republican				
Control	100	4.25 (3.96, 4.55)	3.25 (2.96, 3.55)	1.00 (0.58, 1.42)	22.29	< 0.001	0.07
Distributional fairness framing	100	4.43 (4.14, 4.73)	2.66 (2.37, 2.96)	1.77 (1.35, 2.19)	69.82	< 0.001	0.19
Personal fairness framing	100	4.24 (3.95, 4.54)	2.97 (2.68, 3.27)	1.27 (0.85, 1.69)	35.95	< 0.001	0.11

Note. 95% confidence intervals are reported in parenthesis.

However, only the interaction effect between political orientation and distributional fairness framing was significant ($b_{\text{distributional} \times \text{political orientation}} = -0.77, 95\% \text{ CI } (-1.36, -0.18), t(294) = -2.57, P = 0.011, \eta_p^2 = 0.07$), while the personal fairness framing manipulation did not significantly moderate the effect of political orientation on carbon tax acceptance ($b_{\text{personal} \times \text{political orientation}} = -0.27, 95\% \text{ CI } (-0.86, 0.32), t(294) = -0.90, P = 0.368$). Therefore, we could only support H4a

because the results did not provide enough support for H4b. The interaction effects were mainly driven by Republicans reacting to the message framing manipulations because, while Democrats' reported carbon tax acceptance did not vary significantly between experimental groups ($F(2, 294) = 0.51, P = 0.601, \eta_p^2 = 0.01$), there was a significant difference in mean carbon tax acceptance for Republicans exposed to either the distributional fairness framing, the personal fairness framing or the control group ($F(2, 294) = 3.88, P = 0.022, \eta_p^2 = 0.03$). Results remained robust when controlling for environmental values and libertarian beliefs (See Appendix A).

Figure 2a illustrates how the distributional framing manipulation generated diverging responses, as Democrats reported a higher acceptance than in the control group while Republicans reduced their support. Figure 2b shows that the personal fairness framing performed worse than the distributional fairness framing, and it was unable to significantly alter carbon tax acceptance. The subgroup analysis reported in Appendix A (See Table A.6 and Figure A.4) shows that the distributional framing manipulation only increased carbon tax acceptance for strong Democrats. The loss of Republican support caused by the distributional fairness manipulation was mainly driven by moderate Republicans. The personal fairness manipulation did not significantly alter strong and moderate Democrats' carbon tax acceptance, and it further reduced strong and moderate Republicans' support.

Figure 2. The effect of (a) distributional fairness and (b) personal fairness framings on carbon tax acceptance, moderated by political orientation. *Error bars correspond to 95% confidence intervals.*

5.3 Discussion

Identity-affirming framings that appeal to partisans' concerns influenced carbon tax acceptance. As expected, the distributional fairness framing further polarized responses (i.e., increase Democrats' and reduce Republicans' acceptance), but the personal fairness framing was unable to bridge the partisan gap (i.e., increase Republicans' support, narrowing the difference between Republicans' and Democrats' acceptance levels). This study adds to the climate policy communication literature focused on polarization (e.g., Diamond & Zhou, 2021). Specifically, our findings show that policy labels constitute more than trivial semantic differences (Hardisty et al., 2010).

Among experimental groups, the distributional fairness framing increased carbon tax acceptance the most. However, this increase in policy support was limited to Democrats and came at the cost of reducing Republicans'—already low—support. As confirmed by the manipulation checks, the framing increased the perceived distributional fairness of the tax and made participants think the policy was being endorsed by a Democrat. The drop in Republicans' support was primarily driven by moderate Republicans, whose carbon tax acceptance plummeted when distributional fairness was underscored. Despite the effectiveness of the distributional fairness framing in increasing Democrats' support, this message should be used sparingly to avoid Republicans' backlash. Similarly, Sommer et al. (2022) found that information provision about green spending plans can do more harm than good, and warned that such distributional framings run the risk of “preaching to the converter” (Democrats) while further polarizing the policy debate.

Regarding the personal fairness framing targeted at Republicans, the message did not increase their carbon tax acceptance. This result was contrary to our hypothesis, but other studies departing from framing theory have also found that messages aimed at influencing climate policy cause

reactance among Republicans (e.g. Bolsen, Leeper, et al., 2014). Motivated reasoning seems to exacerbate reactance (Ma et al., 2019), a phenomenon that reinforces pre-existing opinions anytime partisans are exposed to counter-attitudinal arguments (Guess & Coppock, 2020). Reactance predominates in studies focused on policy preferences (Bolsen, Leeper, et al., 2014; Druckman et al., 2013; Hart & Nisbet, 2012). In line with Fremstad et al. (2022), our results suggest that non-partisan frames might be more effective than partisan frames to convince—moderate—Republicans.

Although previous research has successfully used message framing to bridge the partisan gap for general environmental attitudes (Wolsko et al., 2016), a review of experimental interventions shows that consensus does not necessarily translate to specific policy attitudes (Rode et al., 2021). Likewise, we found that a framing targeting Republicans increased their personal fairness perceptions about the carbon tax, but this change did not translate to policy support. Similar intervention studies targeting Republicans have backfired when trying to change skeptics' attitudes about climate change (e.g. Carmichael et al., 2017; Chinn & Hart, 2021; Singh & Swanson, 2017). Moreover, carbon tax opponents tend to overestimate the prevalence of their own views, and trying to correct their misperceptions using information provision only reduces their policy acceptance (Drews et al., 2022).

The reactance observed in Study 2 might be caused by a lack of source credibility. Trust in the messenger is, at least, as important as the message content for avoiding reactance (Song et al., 2018). Although our manipulation conveyed the notion that the carbon tax was endorsed by a Republican, the personal fairness framing was clearly part of an academic survey. Researchers are very different from the kind of non-expert speakers who can better connect with skeptic audiences (Muradova et al., 2020). Besides, policy endorsements from partisan elites increase Democrats' carbon tax acceptance more than Republicans' (Ehret et al. 2018).

6. Implications for carbon pricing policy communication

Our findings suggest that partisans' differences in carbon tax perceptions are mainly generated at explicit level, exacerbating the unconscious tendencies already existing at implicit level. The

theory of politically motivated reasoning, as well as individuals reflecting on their libertarian beliefs, could explain why having more time to respond leads to more extreme responses. If polarization happens to be identity-based, partisans who knowingly report exaggerated opinions about carbon taxes in surveys should still be able to act on their correct beliefs in the real world (Malka & Adelman, 2022). Nevertheless, Malka and Adelman (2022) warn that expressive responding based on political identity is not a minor problem nor a methodological artifact of surveys, but a major determinant of voters' decision process who increasingly engage in identity-expressive political behavior in the real world.

Instead of downplaying the importance of identity-based polarization in the hope partisans are simply exaggerating, communication campaigns could garner support for the carbon tax by presenting the policy in a way that does not activate the identity-protective cognition mechanism. This can be achieved either with non-partisan framings (Fremstad et al., 2022) or selective framing strategies that affirm identity (Zhou, 2016), minimizing the possibility that the new policy information threatens partisans' identity if they agree with it. Specifically, moral appeals that resonate with Republicans have proven to be effective in neutralizing their reactance against climate change communication (Dixon et al., 2017; Wolsko et al., 2016). For example, experimental evidence shows that energy security frames increase carbon tax support among Republicans more than framing the policy as a climate change mitigation instrument (Feldman & Hart, 2018). Carbon pricing communication could thus use frames that resonate with partisans' identity to increase support and avoid climate change frames when targeting Republicans. Online advertising makes such communication campaigns feasible at a large scale: A field experiment conducted by Goldberg et al. (2021) in the US found that message framing via online advertising changed Republicans' attitudes towards climate change in the two congressional districts targeted by the campaign.

7. Limitations and further research

Our results should be taken with caution because individuals' stated intentions do not necessarily lead to actual behaviors (Ajzen, 1991). Voters can react to a polarized environment by disliking

the opposing party for identity-affirming reasons but moderate their own issue positions at the same time (Levendusky & Malhotra, 2016). Further research focused on deeper drivers of polarization can shed light on the relationship between partisan policy perceptions and voters' actual behavior. For example, our research could not rule out other priors and libertarian beliefs as alternative explanations because we did not use explicit partisan cues to measure the affective polarization effect. The OSF page of this research project can be used for replications and empirical generalizations. However, the two-party system is rather unique and the US politics division on environmental issues along party lines hardly applies to other countries.

The polarized responses about carbon tax fairness in Study 1 and policy acceptance in Study 2 were partly attributed to politically motivated reasoning, but this divergence could have also been caused by accuracy-motivated reasoners who trust different sources. Future research should thus distinguish between directional and accuracy motivations at play (Druckman & McGrath, 2019) by measuring and controlling for source credibility but also by manipulating partisan goals (e.g., Bolsen, Druckman, et al., 2014) to understand whether respondents really have a political directional motivation.

If reactance problems caused by source credibility persist, policymakers could explore not making carbon taxes salient to avoid the activation of the identity protective cognition mechanism in the first place. On the one hand, 'hiding' the carbon tax in the final retail price would look like a small modification to the existing energy tax schemes and thus motivated reasoners might perceive carbon pricing less as a partisan policy (Dominioni, 2022). On the other hand, however, carbon tax acceptability is highly reliant on transparency (Maestre-Andrés et al., 2021). Concealing the carbon tax to avoid identity-protective cognition could undermine trust in the government and in the policy, causing further reactance from its critics.

8. Conclusions

The findings presented in this article show that the interplay of affective and cognitive factors drives political polarization over carbon taxes in the US. In Study 1, we compared carbon tax fairness perceptions measured implicitly (i.e., unconscious associations) and explicitly (i.e., stated

beliefs). In line with our predictions, unconscious fairness perceptions about carbon taxes were already polarized, meaning that the divergence in partisans' attitudes originated before cognitive—conscious—factors were involved. These differences increased significantly when Democrats and Republicans explicitly reported their perceptions. Since the main divergence in fairness perceptions occurred at the explicit level—and stated beliefs are considered easier to influence than deeply rooted implicit attitudes—we conclude that Democrats' and Republicans' views on carbon taxes are not irreconcilable. Bridging deliberated polarization requires changing explicit attitudes that arise when reflecting on political ideas and identity.

Identity-based polarization can be bridged because perceptions about the alignment of the policy with own political identity should be malleable. Study 2 showed that appealing to partisans' concerns and using rhetoric familiar to them when presenting the carbon tax influenced their policy support. A manipulation check confirmed that when the carbon tax framing highlighted a progressive revenue redistribution program, carbon taxes were seen as a Democrat-backed policy, while a carbon tax message using personal freedom and free-market rhetoric was regarded as a Republican-backed policy. Compared to the control group, individuals' carbon tax acceptance changed when the policy was framed as backed by their fellow partisans. Democrats reacted to the framing as expected, increasing their carbon tax acceptance when the carbon tax was framed as endorsed by fellow Democrats, while their policy support remained unchanged when the framing made them believe the tax was endorsed by Republicans. However, Republicans did not react to the framing as predicted. Even though Republicans believed a fellow partisan endorsed the carbon tax message, they reacted negatively to it and decreased their policy support. Carbon tax acceptance was even lower when Republicans were presented with a framing targeted at Democrats (i.e., highlighting distributional fairness).

These results emphasize the importance of using identity-affirming framings sparingly, not to exacerbate polarization by mistake. Identity-affirming framings can reduce cognitive dissonance by aligning policy support with own political identity, but they can also backfire if the message source is not credible to carbon tax opponents. In turn, an exaggerated framing to appease carbon tax opponents may also be counterproductive since it may enrage or mislead the existing supporter

base. Therefore, for large policy communication campaigns—when campaigners have limited control over who receives the message—, non-partisan framings will generally be safer than identity-affirming framings. Study 2 results show that our framings caused reactance among Republicans, probably due to a lack of source credibility. Failure to address this lack of credibility might lead, as in our case, to situations in which climate policy communications end up ‘preaching to the converted’: further increasing Democrats’ acceptance at the expense of—even—lower Republican support.

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